

Report on First Round of Benchmarks Deliverable D3.7

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes the first round of benchmarks conducted under the **NEWA validation strategy**. An update of the validation program is provided with a schedule of forthcoming benchmarking activities based on the availability of experimental data. This report is the first of a series of three annual reports on NEWA benchmarks.

The first phase of the project has resulted in three main activities with a common objective of defining a baseline model-chain both at mesoscale and microscale levels.

The **Mesoscale Sensitivity Test** consisted on executing a sensitivity analysis of the WRF model coordinated by the NEWA mesoscale group around four European regions. This activity has been reported separately in deliverable 3.1 and concluded with the definition of a reference WRF set-up that will be used to produce the European Wind Atlas. Validation of this reference WRF configuration will be conducted in connection to the beta run of the wind atlas using available tall mast data from research and industry sites.

The **Ryningsnäs Blind Test** benchmark gathered a group of microscale modelers to simulate the mean profile of an atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) above a heterogeneous forest canopy on flat terrain and neutral atmospheric conditions. This benchmark tested canopy models that can use high-resolution canopy maps generated from aerial lidar scans. The main findings are that the involved modeling groups, using models ranging from advanced industrial codes to state-of-the-art research codes, shows good agreement regarding wind profiles. The magnitude of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) generally matches the observed one, but does not show the same directional dependence as the observed. The inability to model non-neutral conditions was striking. The learning outcome from the benchmark consortium is large and many key questions for future studies in the Hornamossen, i.e., from the extensive Swedish measurement campaign launched within NEWA, benchmark are defined.

The **GABLS3 diurnal-cycle** benchmark for wind energy applications revisited the original case developed by the boundary-layer meteorology community and adapted it to match the specific objectives of NEWA. Here, microscale modelers were asked to demonstrate that they can reproduce a real diurnal cycle with varying atmospheric stability and using input forcing produced offline from a mesoscale model (proxy for a wind atlas database). Mesoscale tendencies generated from WRF were provided as input to drive ABL RANS and LES models. All the models showed good consistency at assimilating tendencies even though some scatter remains depending on the particular settings of each code.

At this stage, we arrive to the first important milestone of the NEWA model-chain development, namely, the definition of a **reference model-chain** that includes:

- A reference WRF configuration derived after sensitivity analysis in various European regions.
- A reference canopy model implementation in microscale ABL models that can use high-resolution aerial lidar scans.

- A methodology for offline coupling of microscale models with mesoscale tendencies and transient turbulence modeling of varying atmospheric stability conditions.

Next round of benchmarks will use experimental data recently produced by NEWA experiments to test these reference models in complex terrain, coastal and offshore environments. Meso-micro methodologies will be compared in terms of annual wind resource statistics using a hierarchy of models of varying fidelity levels. This will allow differentiating methods suitable for planning (wind atlas) or design phases of wind energy projects.

Introduction

The formal V&V framework adopted in NEWA comes from Sandia National Laboratories (Hills et al., 2015), following existing methodologies developed by various American organizations including DoE, NASA, AIAA and ASME¹ (AIAA, 1998; ASME, 2009; Oberkampf et al., 2007; Pitch et al., 2001; Trucano et al., 2002). The framework is also adopted in the frame of the IEA Task 31 Wakebench to establish a model evaluation protocol for wind farm flow models (Sanz Rodrigo and Moriarty, 2015).

An overview of the essential aspects of this framework is provided in deliverable D3.4 (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2016) together with its application to the NEWA context. This includes two instruments:

- the Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT), to identify and prioritize relevant physics and input characterization for wind assessment from mesoscale to microscale modeling, and
- a benchmarking strategy, to execute verification, validation and uncertainty quantification cases alongside the development and testing of the NEWA model-chain as observational data becomes available.

The original benchmarking strategy is reviewed in this report based on the latest update of the experimental database. Then, three validation benchmarks are described and analyzed towards the general goals of the NEWA project.

1. NEWA Benchmarking Strategy

Annex I presents an updated hierarchy of model evaluation activities of the project defined in terms of the test case (dataset) and associated benchmarks, each one with an objective and expected results. The persons in charge of each test case and benchmark are identified as well as the institutions that intend to participate in each one. The associated NEWA reporting milestones are also indicated for internal project management use.

2. WRF Sensitivity Analysis over European Regions

The results of the WRF sensitivity analysis are reported in deliverable 3.1 within a description of the NEWA probabilistic wind atlas approach (Hahmann et al., 2017).

¹ Department of Energy (DoE), National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME)

3. Ryningsnäs Blind Test for Canopy Modeling

3.1. Scope

The idea with this benchmark is to see how well the models can handle input of forest surface and how the resulting predictions of wind speed, wind direction and turbulence kinetic energy compare to the profile measurements from the tower. The benchmark consists of a simple test where one wind speed is simulated from three different angles with slightly different upstream conditions.

3.2. Objectives

Study the capability of today's microscale models to accurately simulate flow in forested terrain. The main research question is how well models can predict the wind profile in a forested landscape with available methods, given a wind speed at 100 to fit the models. The response of the models to changes in ground conditions such as forest cover and terrain elevation is studied, and is extremely relevant to the wind siting process. The topography of the site is mild but the fetch consists of heterogeneous forest cover in all directions, making it useful as a first attempt of forest benchmarking before involving more complex topography.

3.3. Input data

- Wind speed at 98 m: 7.4 ms⁻¹ for both neutral and stable stratification
- Heat flux at 40 m: 200 W/m², Obukhov length $L \approx 185$ m in stable stratification
- Three separate directions are to be modelled: 100°, 240°, 290°. The validation data is taken from those directions $\pm 10^\circ$.
- Forest configuration 40x40 km. The data set is provided as 50x50m averages and 10x10m averages and includes:
 - Ground elevation
 - Tree height
 - PAD (Plant Area Density)

3.4. Validation data

Met mast data for an experiment which ran between November 2010 and February 2012, yielding a total of 10560 hours of available measurements.

A drawing of the instrumental setup is shown in Figure 1.

High frequency 3D-sonic measurements are available at 40, 59, 80, 98, 120, 138 m height. In addition, temperature sensors and cup anemometers are available for the validation.

Figure 1: met mast used in the measurement campaign

3.5. Model runs

Table 1: Suggested model runs

Run #	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3
Stability	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Stable	Stable	Stable
Direction(°)	100±10	240±10	290±10	100±10	240±10	290±10

3.6. Output data

- Profiles from 0-200 m at the heights 1,5,10,15,20,....200. Interpolate if necessary.
 - U, W, direction, TKE (Reynolds stresses if possible)

- These profiles should be taken at the position: $x=6348562$, $y=559493$ In the SWEREF99TM coordinate system (same system as the ground information is given)
- Boundary layer height, u^* , Geostrophic/free stream wind

The wind field in a fixed horizontal grid, 25x25 meters. The grid should at minimum cover the area with 1 km radius around the tower (if the model domain is smaller,

3.7. Activities so far

Around ten modelling groups have participated and the results are being compiled into a scientific paper.

The benchmark opened up for participants in spring 2016 and the benchmark description as well as surface data and canopy data was made available to participants.

A workshop was held in October in Mullsjö near the new field site, i.e., Hornamossen, where we also arranged a visit to the tower and the nearby measuring sites. The idea with the Ryningsnäs site was to immediately start developing methodology for modeling comparison while awaiting the data from the new large measurement site. The Ryningsnäs site consists of one 140 m high met mast.

The models included in the benchmark can broadly be separated into three complexity classes: linear RANS, nonlinear RANS and LES. A very interesting idea with this benchmark was that the groups were provided with forest density data derived from airborne laser scans. These data included ground height, forest height and forest density (forest density had a vertical resolution of 1 m). Two spatial resolutions of 10x10 m and 50x50 m were provided. Almost all groups used these data in some form and it is considered a success that the implementation worked and that the overall level of shear and TKE was reasonable well predicted indicating that the method is a very promising way of minimizing the uncertainties connected to estimating ground and vegetation properties from land use data bases. The results of the benchmark showed that certain model constants configurations in the TKE closure were much more suitable for atmospheric (and specifically forest) boundary layer problems. This was considered an important learning outcome as the optimal set of constant now can be used from the start.

Another striking conclusion of the benchmark activity was the inability of most groups to model non-neutral conditions. The original benchmark included a neutral case and a stably stratified case, but almost all groups failed to provide estimations for the stable case, simply because there was too little experience or the models could not handle non-neutral stratification. Because of that, the group agreed that the next benchmark activity, utilizing data from the new site should challenge the modelers with a full diurnal cycle, i.e. both non-neutral and non-stationary conditions.

The results of the benchmark is currently being compiled into a scientific paper which is aimed for submission in October 2017. At that point the new benchmark, utilizing data from the Swedish NEWA field campaign will be launched. More detailed results, both

quantitative and qualitative will be available with the coming publication, but has naturally already been shared among the benchmark participants and has been generally made accessible for NEWA partners.

3.8. Learning outcomes.

- All the research groups were able to input the very detailed ground data, but the commercial codes could not. The results indicate that uncertainties in estimating roughness parameters can be greatly reduced by using input data based on airborne laser scans as compared to traditional land use data bases.
- The wind profile was generally captured quite well, but there is larger shear in the modelled profile than in the observed one. The shear is over predicted with a magnitude in the order of 10^{-2} s^{-1} .
- The magnitude of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) generally match the observed one, but does not show the same directional dependence as the observed.
- The differences between solver is small compared to the differences between different TKE closures on the same solver.
- The benchmark formulation with target values at 100 m height for both wind speed and wind direction provided some difficulties for the modelers, this was especially true for LES modelling in which re-runs are very time consuming. In the future NEWA forest benchmark, measured geostrophic wind and direction will be provided instead.
- TKE closure using the Sogachev et al. (2012) approach provided consistent results that matched the observations with the following parameter values:
$$\kappa = 0.4, C_{\epsilon 1} = 1.52, C_{\epsilon 2} = 1.833, \sigma_k = 1, \sigma_\epsilon = 3.41 \text{ and } C_\mu = 0.03$$
- Particularly it was observed that C_μ is important for the TKE to shear ratio and is crucial to get the correct turbulence intensity since altering the value drastically changes the predicted magnitude of TKE.

4. GABLS3 Diurnal Cycle for Meso-Micro Modeling

The GABLS3 benchmark has been managed in the Windbench.net portal. The online benchmark guide is reproduced here: <http://windbench.net/gabls-3>

The results of the benchmark were presented at the Wake Conference 2017 in Visby, Sweden, June 2017, and the associated paper is attached to this report in Annex II.

4.1. Scope

The GABLS3 case has been selected in the NEWA project as a baseline exercise for the design of mesoscale-to-microscale methodologies for wind resource assessment. The case is suitable for the development of microscale wind farm models that incorporate

realistic forcing, derived from a mesoscale model, along a typical diurnal case that leads to the development of a nocturnal low-level jet (LLJ). Challenges of this case include: incorporating time- and height-dependent mesoscale forcing in microscale models, turbulence modeling at varying atmospheric stability conditions, defining suitable surface boundary conditions for momentum and heat and characterization of the wind profile in (non-logarithmic) LLJ conditions.

4.2. Data Accessibility

Data is provided open-access for registered participants. For practical reasons, a copy of the GABSL3 observational dataset, made available by KNMI, is provided as well.

4.3. Objectives

Wind-energy specific objectives of the benchmark include:

- Demonstrate the capability of wind energy ABL models to incorporate realistic mesoscale forcing
- Implement surface boundary conditions suitable for wind assessment studies using mesoscale simulation data and/or observations (typical of wind energy campaigns)
- Develop suitable model calibration strategies for wind energy applications or, in other words, how to best use available measurements (typical of wind energy campaigns) to correct meso-micro predictions
- Define suitable metrics for validation of ABL models based on wind energy quantities of interest

By "typical wind energy campaigns" we would like to encourage modellers to prioritize observations that are common place in wind resource assessment campaigns (80 masts with velocity and temperature measurements, lidar profilers measuring up to 400 m).

4.4. Input data

The case set-up and input data of the original GABLS3 case can be found in the KNMI website. This is useful if you want to compare with published results of the original SCM model intercomparison. In the original GABLS3 set-up, the simulated mesoscale tendencies are adjusted to produce a better match with the surface geostrophic wind obtained from a network of synoptic stations and the wind speed at 200-m measured at the Cabauw tower. Initial profiles are based on soundings measured near the Cabauw mast.

Alternatively, you can use inputs generated entirely from a WRF simulation, as described in [1][2]. Here, instead of using observed initial profiles and adjusted mesoscale forcings you can use initial profiles and forcing produced directly from a mesoscale simulation. This is more representative of a wind energy model-chain set-up, where the inputs of a microscale model are generated by a "wind atlas" methodology that doesn't normally include corrections with local measurements. Instead, local adjustments are allowed at

the microscale level by incorporating onsite measurements as if these measurements were part of a typical wind resource assessment campaign.

The WRF simulation is based on a one-way nesting configuration of three concentric square domains centered at the Cabauw site, of the same size 181x181, and at 9, 3 and 1 km horizontal resolution. The vertical grid, approximately 13 km high, is based on 46 terrain-following (eta) levels with 24 levels in the first 1000 m, the first level at approximately 13 m, a uniform spacing of 25 m over the first 300 m and then stretched to a uniform resolution of 600 m in the upper part. The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) land-use surface data, that comes by default with the WRF model, is used together with the unified Noah land-surface model to define the boundary conditions at the surface. Other physical parameterizations used are: the rapid radiative transfer model (RRTM), the Dudhia radiation scheme and the Yonsei University (YSU) first-order PBL scheme. The simulation uses input data from ERA-Interim with a spin-up time of 24 hours. The WRF set-up follows the reference configuration of Kleczek et al [3], who run a sensitivity analysis of WRF showing reasonably good results at reproducing the nocturnal LLJ.

A NetCDF file is provided with the following information:

- Site coordinates and Coriolis parameter
- Time-height 2D arrays of velocity components (U,V,W) and potential temperature (Th)
- Time-height 2D arrays of mesoscale forcings (tendencies): geostrophic wind (U_g, V_g), advective wind (U_{adv}, V_{adv}) and advective potential temperature (Th_{adv})
- Time array of surface-layer quantities: friction velocity (u_{st}), kinematic heat flux (w_t), 2-m temperature (T2), skin temperature (TSK), surface pressure (Psfc)

Figure 2: Time-height contour plots of the longitudinal wind component U and momentum budget terms: $U_{tend} = U_{adv} + U_{cor} + U_{pg} + U_{pbl}$. [1][2]

Units, dimensions and variables description are all provided in the NetCDF file. Momentum tendencies (Figure 2) are provided in $[m s^{-1}]$ and should be multiplied by the

Coriolis parameter to obtain appropriate forces in $[m\ s^{-2}]$. For convenience, we have omitted information about humidity since the assumption of dry-atmosphere is typically adopted by wind energy flow models.

A python script is provided to show how to read the NetCDF input file and extract these variables.

4.5. Validation data

The following quantities of interest (QoI) will be evaluated as described in [1][2], using a reference rotor size of 160 m diameter at a hub-height of 120 m (~ 7 MW turbine):

- Rotor equivalent wind speed (REWS)
- Hub-height wind direction (WDhub)
- Turbulence intensity at hub-height (TIhub)
- Wind shear (power-law exponent α) and wind veer (slope of linear fit to wind direction differences ψ) across the rotor plane
- Surface-layer quantities: T2, ust, wt and z/L

The evaluation consists on time-series plots of these QoIs along the diurnal cycle and mean-absolute error (MAE) integrated over the whole cycle.

4.6. Model runs

The benchmark is mainly developed for microscale models that make use of the input data described above. However, mesoscale or multi-scale (online meso-micro) simulations are also welcome. The following suggestions are provided to guide the model runs:

- We shall use the 2-m temperature (T2) as our most practical reference to deduce the potential temperature surface boundary conditions using Monin Obukhov similarity theory, since this variable is routinely measured in measurement campaigns and is part of the standard output of meteorological models.
- Simulations may be based entirely on the mesoscale input data or incorporate measurements from the Cabauw mast. Priority should be given to measurements that can be found in "typical wind energy campaigns" (80 masts with velocity and temperature measurements, lidar profilers measuring up to 400 m).
- Sensitivity analysis of mesoscale models can be used to quantify the input uncertainty derived from the spread of the ensemble of simulations.
- Online multi-scale simulations models can be used as a reference for microscale models that are coupled to mesoscale asynchronously through the input data. To allow this comparison multi-scale simulations should be also run with ERA-Interim input data.
- Microscale models using Sogachev et al. (2012) k - ϵ turbulence model shall use this set of constants: $\kappa = 0.4$, $C_{\epsilon1} = 1.52$, $C_{\epsilon2} = 1.833$, $\sigma_k = 2.95$, $\sigma_\epsilon = 2.95$ and $C_\mu = 0.03$

If resources allow, please use a spin-up time of 24 hours as in the input data.

4.7. Output data

Data should be provided in a single NetCDF file as described in the python template. The following output variables are requested:

- Time-height 2D arrays of: velocity components, potential temperature and turbulent kinetic energy
- Time 1D array of surface-layer quantities: friction velocity (u_{st} , at 3 m), kinematic heat flux (w_t , at 3 m) and 2-m temperature (T_2)
- Time in hours since 2006-07-01 12:00 UTC
- Heights in meters (please provide model levels at least up to 4000 m)

4.8. References

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5. Conclusions and Outlook

Three benchmarks are summarized herein to report the first phase of the NEWA model evaluation strategy. With this, we arrive to the first important milestone of the NEWA model-chain development, namely, the definition of a reference model-chain that includes:

- A reference WRF configuration derived after sensitivity analysis in various European regions and blindly tested with industry data provided by Vestas
- A reference canopy model implementation in microscale ABL models that can use high-resolution aerial lidar scans
- A methodology for offline coupling of microscale models with mesoscale tendencies and transient turbulence modeling of varying atmospheric stability conditions.

Next round of benchmarks will use experimental data recently produced by NEWA experiments to test these reference models in complex terrain, coastal and offshore environments. Meso-micro methodologies will be compared in terms of annual wind resource statistics using a hierarchy of models of varying fidelity levels. This will allow differentiating methods suitable for planning (wind atlas) or design phases of wind energy projects.

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Annex I: NEWA Validation hierarchy as of June 2017

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-Synop	Fidel González Rouco (UCM)	Complement validation where tall masts are not available and carry out regionalization to characterize the wind climates across Europe	1,2,4,5,8	Elena García (CIEMAT)	Extend categorization of errors to a wider diversity of site and wind climate conditions, especially in regions without tall mast measurements	UCM, CIEMAT, LU (Latvia only)	M27	M36 (D3.8), M48 (D3.9)
		Predictability at various scales. Model results will be evaluated against observational data sets; re-analyses and observational data sets wherever available.		Albert Soret (BSC)	Validation of predictability atlas	BSC, CENER	M27	M42 (D4.2)
		Extreme winds using stations with 20+ years (combine with Tall mast data where available)	4,7	Xiaoli G. Larsen (DTU)	Validation of Vref atlas	DTU, CIEMAT, UCM	M12	M42 (D4.2)
		Uncertainty quantification. ECMWF-EPS dataset will be used as proxy for developing the methodology for probabilistic wind assessment.	1,8,15,16,17	Sergio Fernández (UCM)	Characterization of uncertainty in probabilistic models by an optimal spread index.	UCM	M8	M42 (D4.4)
NEWA-Sensitivity	Andrea Hahmann (DTU)	Define WRF set-up methodology. Sensitivity analysis at various EU subdomains. Preliminary analysis around reference tall masts	2	Andrea Hahmann (DTU)	A reference WRF set-up will be defined as baseline for optimization in the validation process	DTU, CIEMAT, UCM, LU, ITU, ForWind, Wtech, DNV-GL	M8	M27 (D3.1)

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-Tall-Blind	Andrea Hahmann (DTU)	Blind test using tall mast data from industry (Vestas) to assess skill of different meso-micro methodologies. The set of evaluation metrics will be used in connection to other datasets as a result of the CfWD	4,8	Bjarke Tobias Olsen (DTU)	Validation of wind assessment methodologies and categorization of errors in terms of site and climate complexities. Baseline validation results for first release of NEWA model-chain	DTU, Vestas	M15	M36 (D3.8)
	Elena Cantero (CENER)	Other blind tests resulting from CfWD at various stages of the project, using the same metrics developed with the Vestas case	4,8	Laura Frías (CENER) Spanish data, Andrea (DTU) Danish data, etc	Beta run Production Run	DTU, CIEMAT, UCM, LU, ITU, ForWind, Wtech	M27 M36	M36 (D3.8) M48 (D3.9)
NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge	Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)	Determine the applicability range of meso-micro methodologies for wind resource assessment within the NEWA validation domain	1,2,4,5,8	Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)	Phase 1: Cabauw, Fino1 and Alaiz (M36) Phase 2: Kassel, Perdigao, Hornamossen, Alaiz	CENER, DTU, BSC, ForWind, IWES, UPorto, ATM Pro, Wtech, UCM-CIEMAT, Vortex	M25 M36	M36 (D3.8) M48 (D3.9)

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-GABLS3	Fred Bosveld (KNMI)	GABLS3 diurnal cycle at the Cabauw site in the Netherlands. Developed by the boundary-layer meteorology community	1,4,6,8,9,14,17	Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)	GABLS3 revisited for wind energy. Baseline case for meso-micro coupling methods dealing with realistic forcing	CENER, BSC, DTU, UPorto, KUL, CUBoulder	M16	M29 (D3.7)
NEWA-Ryningsnas	Stefan Ivanell (UU)	Blind test for the generation of wind profiles over an heterogeneous forested canopy in nearly-flat terrain. Near-neutral conditions for three wind direction sectors	10,13,14	Stefan Ivanell (UU)	Baseline validation study for ABL microscale models above a forest canopy	CENER, ForWind, DTU, Vestas, UU, WRD, Siemens	M12	M29 (D3.7)
NEWA-Hornamossen	Stefan Ivanell (UU)	Experiments with a 180 m met mast in combination with remote sensing instruments along a line of 14 km. (in total about 12 remote sensing instruments) The site has heterogeneous forested canopy in moderate complex terrain. The benchmark will be used for model validation for both micro and mesoscale models.	2,4,8,9,11,11,13	Stefan Ivanell (UU)	Benchmark in 4 stages of increasing complexity: 1) flat ABL inflow, 2) flat ABL+canopy, 3) ABL + terrain, 4) ABL + terrain + canopy, in neutral, stable and diurnal cycle	CENER, ForWind, DTU, Vestas, UU, WRD, Siemens	M27	M36 (D3.8), M48 (D3.9)
NEWA-Mut	Sibel Menteş (ITU)	Verification of simplified microscale model. Grid dependency study in complex terrain	11	Sibel Menteş (ITU)	Quantification of numerical errors at different grid resolutions. Definition of methodology for microscale model set-up	ITU	M18	M36 (D3.8)

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-RUNE	Alfredo Peña (DTU)	Development of coastal transition	9,10,11,12,14	Alfredo Peña (DTU)	Simulate a 4-month period and evaluate coastal transition at three heights	ForWind, DTU, Wtech, BSC	M25	M36 (D3.8)
NEWA-Balcony	Ebba Dellwik (DTU)	Simulation of heterogeneous forested site - validation with lidar horizontal scans	4,10,13,14	Dalibor Cavar (DTU)	Characterize heterogeneous canopy flow based on lidar scans and simulations	DTU, U.Porto?	M24	M36 (D3.8)
NEWA-LIDARFerryLines	Julia Gottschall (IWES)	Mesoscale validation study for near offshore wind fields under different stability conditions (depends on available data)	12,14	Björn Witha (ForWind)	Knowledge on WRF's ability to capture the marine boundary layer in near shore regions	ForWind, DTU	M29	M36 (D3.8)
+ Satellite Data	Charlotte Hasager (DTU)							
		Microscale validation study: Land-sea transition, verify streaks with LES and ABL microscale models (compare with LiDAR and WRF results and satellite data)	9,10,11,12,14	Björn Witha (ForWind)	Baseline validation study for LES and ABL microscale models for land sea transition with offshore wind speed streaks	ForWind	M33	M42 (D4.2)
	Andrea Hahmann (DTU)	Mesoscale validation study: occurrence of low-level jets in obs and models and their influence in the coupling between meso- and micro	4,8,9,14	Patrick Volker (DTU)	Methodology for the generalization of wind climatologies when low-level jets exist and they impact the wind climate	ForWind, DTU	M12	M42 (D4.2)

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-Kassel	Paul Kuehn (IWES)	Verification of simplified microscale model. Grid dependency study in complex terrain	11	Chi-Yao Chang (IWES)	Quantification of numerical errors at different grid resolutions. Definition of methodology for microscale model set-up	IWES	M8	M12 (D3.3)
		Characterization of canopy and testing of different canopy and surface roughness models	10,13	Martin Dörenkämper (IWES)	Development of numerically and physically consistent model regarding turbulent transports	IWES, ForWind, CENER, BSC, ATM-PRO, VENTA	M27	M36 (D3.8)
		Validation of mean flow for the SSW wind direction under different thermal stratification classes based on mesh sensitivity study and measure campaign	9,10,11,13	Martin Dörenkämper (IWES)	Evaluation of the impact of the wake from Rödeser Berg upstream on the 200m met mast location		M27	M36 (D3.8)
	Merge with NEWA Meso-Micro	Validation of NEWA model-chain over the experimental campaign period	1,4, 9,10,11,13	Martin Dörenkämper (IWES)	Full-validation of model-chain including uncertainty quantification	IWES, ATM-PRO	M27	M48 (D3.9)
NEWA-Perdigao	José L. Palma (UPorto)	Verification of simplified microscale model. Grid dependency study in complex terrain	11	Andreas Bechmann (DTU)	Quantification of numerical errors at different grid resolutions. Definition of methodology for microscale model set-up	DTU, BSC	M8	M12 (D3.3)

Test Case (dataset)	TC Manager	Benchmarking objectives	PIRT	Benchmark Manager	Expected results	Participants	Start	Due
NEWA-Perdigao (cont.)	José L. Palma (UPorto)	Validation of NW sector perpendicular to the eastern ridge (46 azimuth)	9,10,11,14	José L. Palma (UPorto)	Evaluation of flow pattern over the ridges	ITU, CENER, ForWind, CENAERO, BSC, ATM-PRO	M27	M36 (D3.8)
		Validation of SW sector perpendicular to the western ridge (231 azimuth)	9,10,11,15					
NEWA-Alaiz	Elena Cantero (CENER)	Verification of simplified microscale model. Grid dependency study in complex terrain	11	Roberto A. Chávez (CENER)	Quantification of numerical errors at different grid resolutions. Definition of methodology for microscale model set-up	CENER, BSC	M8	M12 (D3.3)
		Blind Test. Validation of mean flow for the northerly and southerly wind sector under various stabilities (cycle of varying stability) based on intensive campaign	4,9,10,11,13	Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)	Evaluation of the impact of the wake from Tajonar hill upstream on the Alaiz wind conditions	CENER, ITU, BSC	M40	M48 (D3.9)
	Merge with NEWA Meso-Micro	Validation of NEWA model-chain over the experimental campaign period	1,4,5,8,15, 16,17	Javier Sanz Rodrigo (CENER)	Full-validation of model-chain including uncertainty quantification	CENER, ITU, CIEMAT, UCM, ATM-PRO	M36	M48 (D3.9)
	Merge with NEWA Meso-Micro	Validate the methodology developed for the ECMWF EPS by probabilistic simulations carried out with WRF mesoscale model. Experimental data of Alaiz field campaign will be used for the validation.	1,2,3,5,8,15,16,17	Sergio Fernández (UCM)	Quantification of numerical errors in a mesoscale probabilistic wind forecast. Icing risk could also be estimated.	UCM	M18	M48 (D3.9)

**Annex II: GABLS3 Diurnal Cycle for Wind Energy Applications.
Reprint of Wake Conference 2017 paper**

Results of the GABLS3 diurnal-cycle benchmark for wind energy applications

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Abstract. We present results of the GABLS3 model intercomparison benchmark revisited for wind energy applications. The case consists of a diurnal cycle, measured at the 200-m tall Cabauw tower in the Netherlands, including a nocturnal low-level jet. The benchmark includes a sensitivity analysis of WRF simulations using two input meteorological databases and five planetary boundary-layer schemes. A reference set of mesoscale tendencies is used to drive microscale simulations using RANS k - ϵ and LES turbulence models. The validation is based on rotor-based quantities of interest. Cycle-integrated mean absolute errors are used to quantify model performance. The results of the benchmark are used to discuss input uncertainties from mesoscale modelling, different meso-micro coupling strategies (online vs offline) and consistency between RANS and LES codes when dealing with boundary-layer mean flow quantities. Overall, all the microscale simulations produce a consistent coupling with mesoscale forcings.

1. Introduction

The increasing growth of wind turbines, with rotor tip heights approaching 200 m, and wind farm clusters extending for tens of kilometers, is pushing the wind farm flow modeling community to consider effective ways of integrating forcing from large meteorological processes in the simulation of the flow at wind farm scale based on computational fluid dynamic (CFD) models. The dynamics of these forcings determine the interplay between the wind climatology, relevant for the assessment of the wind resource, and the wind conditions relevant for wind turbine siting.

A recent review of state-of-the-art methodologies for mesoscale-to-microscale modeling is provided in Sanz Rodrigo et al [1]. Outstanding challenges include: coupling of codes dealing with fundamental differences in terms of physical hypothesis and numerical methods, lack of suitable parameterization in the "terra incognita" [2] that links mesoscale and microscale turbulence processes, and lack of a systematic evaluation procedure that can identify the source of modeling errors. Additionally, for the wind energy community, design conditions are almost entirely based on idealized turbulence and boundary-layer models rather than recognizing and classifying wind conditions that account for mesoscale forcing in design standards.

With these challenges in mind, the boundary-layer meteorology community has conducted a series of model intercomparison GEWEX Atmospheric Boundary Layer Studies (GABLS) [3]. The third GABLS benchmark deals with a diurnal cycle observed at the Cabauw meteorological tower in the Netherlands, under relatively stationary synoptic conditions, that lead to the development of a strong nocturnal low-level jet (LLJ) [4][5]. Model intercomparison results for single-column models (SCM) are reported in [6].

This benchmark has been revisited by the wind energy community to help design meso-micro methodologies for resource assessment and design tools, in particular: incorporating time- and height-dependent mesoscale forcing in microscale models, turbulence modeling at varying atmospheric stability conditions, defining suitable surface boundary conditions for momentum and heat and characterization of the wind profile in (non-logarithmic) LLJ conditions [7]. Initial results, using a single-column model (SCM) as proxy for microscale 3D models, show how adding more realistic mesoscale forcing systematically leads to better performance considering cycle-aggregated rotor-based quantities of interest. Still, a large bias is observed in the hour-to-hour evolution of the vertical wind profile due to the inherent input uncertainty from the mesoscale model [8][9].

This paper summarizes the results of the Windbench/GABLS3 model intercomparison benchmark, discussing three topics: characterization of uncertainties in the input forcing, methodologies for meso-micro coupling, and consistency of turbulence models at different fidelity levels.

2. The Windbench/GABLS3 Benchmark

The GABLS3 original set-up is described in Bosveld et al. [5]. The case analyzes the period from 12:00 UTC 1 July to 12:00 UTC 2 July 2006, at the Cabauw Experimental Site for Atmospheric Research (CESAR), located in the Netherlands (51.971°N, 4.927°E). The elevation of the site is approximately -0.7 m, surrounded by relatively flat terrain characterized by grassland, fields and some scattered tree lines and villages. The roughness length for the wind direction sector of interest (60° - 120°) is 15 cm.

The CESAR measurements are carried out at a 200-m tower, free of obstacles up to a few hundred meters in all directions. The measurements include 10-min averaged vertical profiles of wind speed, wind direction, temperature and humidity at heights 10, 20, 40, 80, 140 and 200 m, as well as surface radiation and energy budgets. Turbulence fluxes are also monitored at four heights: 3, 60, 100 and 180 m. A RASS profiler measures wind speed, wind direction and virtual temperature above 200 m.

The original GABLS3 setup uses a simplified set of forcing terms that was obtained by piecewise linear approximations of the mesoscale tendencies in RACMO numerical weather prediction model to obtain a better agreement of the wind speed at 200m. In our model intercomparison we will use directly the input forcings derived from mesoscale, as described in the next section, without calibration against observations. This is in favor of testing a general methodology for offline coupling of mesoscale and microscale models.

The GABLS3 benchmark for wind energy is published as a Windbench repository in [7].

2.1. Reference WRF simulation: Input Data for Microscale Models

Input forcing for most of the microscale models (excepting VENTOS[®]/M) is derived from a mesoscale simulation using the Weather Research and Forecasting model WRF-ARW v3.8 [10]. Following previous work from Kleczek et al [11], the reference WRF simulation is based on a one-way nesting configuration of three concentric square domains centered at the Cabauw site, of the same size (Figure 1) based on a 181x181 points grid with 9, 3 and 1 km horizontal resolution. The vertical grid, approximately 13 km high, is based on 46 terrain-following (eta) levels with 24 levels in the first 1000 m, the first level at approximately 13 m, a uniform spacing of 25 m over the first 300 m and then stretched to a uniform resolution of 600 m in the upper part. The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) land-use surface data, that comes by default with the WRF model, is used together with the unified Noah land-surface model to define the boundary conditions at the surface. Other physical parameterizations used are: the rapid radiative transfer model (RRTM), the Dudhia radiation scheme and the Yonsei University (YSU) first-order PBL scheme [12]. The simulation uses input data from

ERA-Interim [13] with a spin-up time of 24 hours. The input forcing of VENTOS[®]/M differs from the other mesoscale models and is discussed below.

Time and height-dependent mesoscale forcing is extracted directly from the momentum budget components (so-called “tendencies” in WRF) after filtering out fluctuations at the grid-resolution scale by spatially averaging data from a 9-km wide 3x3 grid around the site and using a 1-hour rolling window on the time series. More details about this meso-micro coupling method and a sensitivity analysis of rotor-averaged forcing on the filter set-up are discussed in [9].

2.2. Validation Data and Metrics

The performance of the models is based on quantities of interest relevant for wind energy applications. These quantities are evaluated across a reference rotor span of 160 m, between 40 and 200 m, characteristic of an 8-MW large wind turbine. Besides hub-height wind speed S_{hub} and direction WD_{hub} , it is relevant to consider the rotor-equivalent wind speed $REWS$, the turbulence intensity (not evaluated here), the wind speed shear α , and the wind direction shear or veer ψ .

The $REWS$ is especially suitable to account for wind shear in wind turbine power performance tests [14]. The $REWS$ is the wind speed corresponding to the kinetic energy flux through the swept rotor area, when accounting for the vertical shear:

$$REWS = \left[\frac{1}{A} \sum_i (A_i S_i^3 \cos \beta_i) \right]^{-1/3} \quad (1)$$

where A is the rotor area and A_i are the horizontal segments that separate vertical measurement points of horizontal wind speed S_i across the rotor plane. The $REWS$ is here weighted by the cosine of the angle β_i of the wind direction WD_i with respect to the hub-height wind direction to account for the effect of wind veer [15].

Wind shear is defined by fitting a power-law curve across the rotor wind speed points S_i :

$$S_i = S_{hub} \left(\frac{z_i}{z_{hub}} \right)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

Similarly, wind veer is defined as the slope ψ of the linear fit of the wind direction difference:

$$\beta_i = \psi (z_i - z_{hub}) \quad (3)$$

To evaluate simulations and measurements consistently, these quantities are obtained after resampling, by linear interpolation, velocity and wind direction vertical profiles at 10 points across the rotor area and then computing the $REWS$ and the shear functional fits. While these fitting functions are commonly used in wind energy, their suitability in LLJ conditions is questionable. The regression coefficient from the fitting can be used to determine this suitability.

A rolling average with a window size of one hour is applied to simulation and observational data to remove the impact of high frequency fluctuations in the analysis.

Validation results are quantified in terms of the mean absolute error (MAE):

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\chi_{pred} - \chi_{obs}| \quad (4)$$

where χ is any of the above mentioned quantities of interest, predicted ($pred$) or observed (obs), and N is the number of samples evaluated in the time series.

3. Participating Models

Table 1 shows a list of the models participating in the model intercomparison benchmark. The microscale models do not include humidity, which is not relevant in this case since the selection criteria for the cycle excluded wet conditions.

Table 1: Summary of model simulations. Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (MOST) surface boundary conditions use either heat flux (H), 2-m (T_2) or skin temperature (T_{SK}) from WRF

Name	Input	Turbulence	z -Levels	Surface B.C.
WRF-YSU (ref)	ERA Interim	YSU	46	Noah
WRF	ERA Interim, GFS	MYJ, MYNN, QNSE, TEMF, YSU	46	Noah
WRF-YSU_LES	ERA Interim	LES-TKE	101	Noah
WRF-VentosM_ke	ERA Interim	YSU/ k - ϵ	70	MOST, H
CFDWind1D_ke	WRF (ref)	k - ϵ	301	MOST, T_2
Alya-CFDWind1D_ke	WRF (ref)	k - ϵ	500	MOST, T_2
Ellipsys1D_ke	WRF (ref)	k - ϵ	512	MOST, T_{SK}
Ellipsys3D_ke	WRF (ref)	k - ϵ	192	MOST, T_{SK}
Ellipsys3D_LES	WRF (ref)	Smagorinsky	128	MOST, T_{SK}
SP-Wind_LES	WRF (ref)	LES-TKE	500	MOST, T_2

3.1. WRF

We use the Advanced Research Weather forecasting model (WRF) version 3.8.1 [10] configured with three nested domains with grid sizes of 27, 9, and 3 km (Figure 1). All model domains have 61 x 61 horizontal grid points and are centered at the Cabauw tower. We use the same vertical grid as in the WRF-YSU (ref) simulation (see Section 2.1), with 46 eta levels defined to increase the vertical resolution in the lowest part of the planetary boundary layer (PBL). The boundary conditions at the surface are defined by the default USGS land-use surface data and the unified Noah land-surface model. The rapid radiative transfer model (RRTM) and the Dudhia radiation scheme are also used. All simulations are spun-up for 24 hours.

We perform a sensitivity analysis varying PBL schemes and global input data, similar to Kleczek et al. [11]. The first of the selected PBL schemes is Yonsei University (YSU) [12], a non-local, first-order closure scheme. Other PBL schemes used in this study are the Mellor–Yamada–Janjic (MYJ) [16], Mellor–Yamada–Nakanishi–Niino (MYNN2.5) [17], and Quasi-Normal Scale Elimination (QNSE) [18], which are classified as local, 1.5-order turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) closure schemes. Total Energy Mass Flux (TEMF) is the final PBL scheme tested and is classified as a hybrid local/non-local, 1.5-order closure scheme [19]. We assess the sensitivity of WRF to input data by running each of the five PBL schemes with two different sources of input data: ERA-Interim [13] and GFS reanalysis. This ensemble of simulations is used in this study to quantify the spread of mesoscale solutions that could be input into the microscale simulations.

Figure 1: Model domain arrangement, with the red star indicating the center of each domain representing the Cabauw tower.

3.2. WRF-LES

Five additional telescopic nests are added to the reference mesoscale set-up of 3 nests to physically downscale, using one-way coupling, to a resolution of 12.5 m in the innermost domain using large-eddy simulation (LES). All domains use a 181x181 horizontal grid. The finest three nests are refined vertically to double the number of levels and obtain an isotropic grid of 12.5 m in the lowest 300 m. A prognostic equation for TKE is solved for the LES subgrid-scale model [23], using the WRF default constants [10]. The time step is reduced from 60 s in the outermost domain to 0.2 s in the innermost nest. Since the cycle starts from unstable atmospheric conditions, spin-up is deemed unnecessary. Hence, the first few hours of the cycle are transitioning to reach equilibrium with the mesoscale boundary conditions.

Mean flow profiles are obtained by spatial averaging over a 1-km wide horizontal box. Fluctuations about the mean flow within this box are used to compute the TKE .

3.3. VENTOS[®]/M

The VENTOS[®]/M computer code is an atmospheric flow solver employing a one-way dynamical coupling methodology, where WRF model simulation results are used as initial and boundary conditions. It solves the URANS equations assuming anelastic fluid, together with a transport equation for potential temperature and a k - ϵ turbulence model [20].

The WRF simulation follows the reference set-up described in Section 3.1 with few differences, namely the software version was WRF-ARW v3.6.1 and a fourth nesting level was added, increasing the downscaling to 1-km horizontal resolution. Physical parameterizations, grid dimensions, nesting grid ratios and the simulation spin-up time were kept equal to the reference simulation.

The VENTOS[®]/M domain encompasses 12x12 km². Centered on Cabauw, the horizontal resolution was kept constant at 160 m within a square area of 3x3 km², afterwards expanding towards the boundaries. At each vertical level the horizontal grid was composed of 47x47 control volumes. The vertical grid consisted of 10 km columns with 70 control volumes, expanding from 4 m above the surface to 730 m at the domain top, where a 4-km Rayleigh damping layer was set. The simulation time-step was 1.5 s and the boundary conditions were updated every 5 minutes. The simulation spin-up time was 12 hours, less than the WRF simulation. Similarly to WRF-LES, the results were smoothed through spatial averaging using 1-km wide horizontal boxes. The VENTOS[®]/M model surface boundary condition is based on Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (MOST) functions and a prescribed surface heat flux, as such quantity is expected to be less sensitive to height discrepancies between the mesoscale and microscale orographies. As heat-flux boundary conditions are not suitable to differentiate between intermittent and fully-turbulent regimes [21], the VENTOS[®]/M model always assumes the latter, which is not appropriate if stratification conditions are indeed very stable.

3.4. CFDWind

CFDWind1D is a python-based finite-difference code. The single-column model (SCM) is used as a prototype to design the CFDWind 3D model [9]. They are both based on unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (URANS) equations using the k - ϵ model of Sogachev et al [23] with constants: $C_{\epsilon 1} = 1.52$, $C_{\epsilon 2} = 1.833$, $\sigma_k = 2.95$, $\sigma_\epsilon = 2.95$ and $C_\mu = 0.03$.

The SCM is solved on a 4-km long log-linear vertical grid with 301 levels using a time step of 1 s. Pressure gradient and advection forcings are lumped together as a time and height-dependent equivalent geostrophic wind that enters momentum equations as source terms. The advection temperature tendency is also added as a source term in the potential temperature equation. No-slip conditions are defined for momentum equations at the surface. Surface boundary conditions for potential temperature are defined based on MOST, inferring the surface temperature by prescribing the diurnal 2-m temperature from the mesoscale input data and using the dynamic surface-layer friction velocity and heat flux as described in [9].

3.5. Alya-CFDWind

Alya-CFDWind1D is a fortran-based finite-elements code equivalent to CFDWindSCM. Similarly, the model is used at early-stage design and as a precursor of the in-house 3D model Alya-CFDWind for

numerical modelling of wind farms [24][25]. The same set of k - ϵ constants than CFDWind1D is used in this study.

The 1D mesh is 4-km tall using 500 vertical elements with a geometrically growing rate from 0.5 m up to 10 m. The time step is set to 10 s.

3.6. *Ellipsys3D*

The EllipSys3D code [26][27] is an in-house multiblock finite volume solver for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in general curvilinear coordinates. The code uses a collocated variable arrangement, where revised Rhie/Chow interpolation is used to avoid odd/even pressure coupling. The code is parallelized with Message Passing Interface (MPI) for executions on distributed/shared memory machines, using a non-overlapping domain decomposition technique.

The URANS case is based on k - ϵ model [22], with the same set of constants than the other URANS models of the benchmark. The problem is solved on a 6-km high vertical domain with 192 tanh stretched grid points using a time step of 1 s.

No-slip wall boundary condition at the bottom and a symmetry boundary condition at the top were applied. Periodic boundaries in both horizontal directions were used to mimic the 1D SCM basic setup. Pressure gradient and momentum advection forcings together with the temperature tendencies are included in the code in a way completely analogous to the procedure presented for the CFDWindSCM code [9].

In the LES case, the 4x4x4 km domain was discretized by 128x128x128 equidistantly spaced grid points, and Smagorinsky SGS model is used. Previously described URANS boundary conditions and time stepping are also applied in the LES case. EllipSys1D [28] is a recent “stripped down” version of EllipSys3D. The basic 3D URANS set-up was also applied in the 1D case. Only 512 tanh stretched grid points were used for discretizing the 6-km high vertical domain.

3.7. *SP-Wind*

SP-Wind is an in-house LES code developed at KU Leuven [29][30][31] for research on the simulation and optimization of turbulent flows. SP-Wind solves the Boussinesq form of the conservation equations for mass, momentum and potential temperature on a three-dimensional Cartesian grid. The horizontal directions are discretized with pseudo-spectral schemes, while the vertical direction uses a fourth-order energy-conservative finite difference scheme. Time integration is performed using a classic four-stage fourth-order Runge—Kutta scheme. The subgrid-scale stress and heat flux are computed with a prognostic TKE model [22], and the surface boundary conditions are imposed using classic Monin-Obukhov similarity theory [32] with standard stability correction functions [33].

The LES is solved on a horizontally periodic domain of 5x5x5 km with 400x400x500 grid points. The vertical grid has a uniform spacing of 5 m in the first 2 km, above which it is stretched to a maximum grid size of 40 m. A Rayleigh damping layer is added above 4 km. Initial profiles, mesoscale forcing and surface temperature (inferred from the 2-m temperature) are all extracted from mesoscale WRF simulations as in [9].

In view of the large computational cost, no spin-up time is used for the LES simulations. Analysis of the vertical profiles of turbulent kinetic energy shows that the positive surface heat flux at UTC 2006-07-01 12:00 leads to intense generation of turbulence, which rapidly fills up the entire boundary layer and reduces the transition time to less than one hour.

4. Results

4.1. *Input uncertainties: Sensitivity Analysis at Mesoscale*

We conduct a sensitivity analysis on the impacts of PBL scheme and global input data on WRF. Atmospheric profiles of potential temperature (θ), moisture (q) and winds (S , WD) over Cabauw at midnight LT on 2006-07-02 illustrate noticeable spread in the model output by the different configurations (Figure 2). Most of the configurations exhibit very similar temperature (Figure 2a) and wind (Figure 3c,d) profiles, while more spread is evident in the moisture profiles (Figure 2b). Further,

the TEMF-GFS (orange open squares) appears to deviate most from the other configurations, most noticeably in the lowest layers of the potential temperature, moisture, and wind speed profiles. The YSU-ERA (green filled dots), the reference mesoscale model used as input for the microscale simulations in this study, shows good agreement to the low-level moisture observations from the Cabauw tower (black dots), but overestimates the winds and the slope of the temperature inversion to a similar degree as the other configurations. Aside from the large difference in the TEMF-GFS and TEMF-ERA output, input data appear to have little impact on the model solution in this particular case, suggesting the input datasets agree on the larger-scale forcing, unlike other cases which show more spread between input datasets.

Figure 2: Atmospheric profiles of (a) potential temperature (θ), (b) water vapor mixing ratio (q), (c) wind speed (S), and (d) wind direction (WD) over Cabauw at midnight LT on 2006-07-02.

Time series of the same variables plotted over the 24-hour period between UTC 2006-07-01 1200 and 2006-07-02 1200 at 80 m show a similar spread between the PBL scheme and input data configurations (Figure 3). The TEMF-GFS again deviates most from the other simulations and the Cabauw observations, especially in the moisture (Figure 3b) and wind speed (Figure 3c) data. The other configurations form a generally narrow spread of output data. In particular, the time series of 80-m potential temperature (Figure 3a) exhibits a spread of ~ 2 K between the configurations, giving the whole ensemble a potential temperature bias consistently between -1 and -4 K. For the moisture and wind time series (Figure 3b-d), the ensemble of configurations frequently envelope the Cabauw observations during the 24-hour period, which may allude to minimal errors caused by choice of PBL scheme and input data on the microscale simulations. Similar conclusions may be drawn from time series of friction velocity (u^*), PBL height ($PBL\ h$), latent heat flux (LE), and sensible heat flux (H) over the same 24-hour period at Cabauw (Figure 4). The greatest differences between the configurations is the TEMF-GFS friction velocity and the TEMF-ERA PBL height. The largest spread of output data is present in the PBL height, while the latent and sensible heat fluxes have the smallest spread. The ensemble of configurations generally overestimated latent and sensible heat fluxes during the day when compared to Cabauw observations, with fewer error during the night.

Figure 3: Time series of 80-m (a) potential temperature (Θ), (b) water vapor mixing ratio (q), (c) wind speed (S), and (d) wind direction (WD) over Cabauw during the 24-hour period between UTC 2006-07-01 1200 and 2006-07-02 1200.

Figure 4: Time series of (a) friction velocity (u_*), (b) planetary boundary layer height ($PBL\ h$), (c) latent heat flux (LE), and (d) sensible heat flux (H) over Cabauw during the 24-hour period between UTC 2006-07-01 1200 and 2006-07-02 1200.

These results show that, excluding the TEMF, choice of input data has a near-negligible impact on the WRF output for this particular case, although input boundary condition datasets exhibit stronger influence in other cases [34]. Rather, differences in both the vertical profiles (Figure 2) and the time series (Figure 3 and Figure 4) between the tested configurations appear to be caused more so by choice of PBL scheme. Despite this dependence on PBL scheme, the ensemble of choices tends to maintain a consistent spread near the observations, with the only significant biases evident in the potential temperature and daytime latent and sensible heat fluxes. The greatest differences between PBL schemes occur in the PBL height calculations (Figure 4b). PBL heights were determined via direct output from each scheme, where each scheme uses a different approach that contributed to the scatter in the data. In the YSU and TEMF schemes, the PBL height is diagnosed from the bulk Richardson

number [12] [19]. For the local PBL schemes (MYJ, MYNN, and QNSE), PBL height is diagnosed as the height where prognostic TKE decreases to a sufficiently small value ($0.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, and $0.01 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively) [16] [17] [18]. Overall, the nontrivial spread in mesoscale forcings should be considered when making a choice in PBL scheme for a simulation that will be used as forcing for a microscale simulation.

4.2. Consistency among LES and RANS Microscale Models

All of the microscale models produce similar patterns of the diurnal cycle, demonstrating the effectiveness of the offline coupling methodology. Figure 5 shows contour plots of the evolution of the vertical profile of mean flow quantities computed by the participating models compared to the observations on the top row. The second row corresponds to the reference mesoscale model that is used to derive input forcings and boundary conditions to drive the microscale simulations. Since no higher-resolution terrain or land cover information is added at microscale, we can assume that this mesoscale simulation is already a good reference for microscale models to verify a correct implementation of the meso-micro methodology. The differences in the mean flow arise from the different ways each model represents turbulence, which is noticed in the *TKE* contour plots.

The ensemble mean of the WRF simulations used in the sensitivity analysis is plotted in the third row. By ensemble averaging, we obtain a better match with the observations than by using any single WRF simulation – this result was also seen for the LLJ cases discussed in [34]. The ensemble here provides a better prediction of the LLJ with a distinct velocity maximum around midnight instead of a broader double-peak as in the reference WRF simulation.

The microscale models diverge in their estimates of rotor-based quantities of interest. Time series of rotor-based quantities of interest are shown in Figure 6. The spread of the models for *REWS* is around 2 m s^{-1} and around 15° in terms of WD_{hub} . The spread in terms of wind shear and wind veer is also large specially during nighttime stable conditions. Vertical profiles of wind speed and direction at midnight (Figure 7) show how the models capture the characteristics of the LLJ. The phase error in the input data dominates the bias in the simulations; this input error cannot be corrected at microscale by simply changing the turbulence model.

Table 2 summarizes the differences between the simulations and observations in terms of (4) with respect to observations (MAE_{obs}) and with respect to the reference WRF simulation (MAE_{ref}). These are differences integrated over the whole diurnal cycle; therefore mixing all kinds of surface stability and large-scale conditions into a single quantity. We shall focus on the MAE_{ref} to quantify the impact of choosing a different turbulence model at microscale.

Table 2: MAE with respect to observations and to the reference mesoscale simulation.

	<i>REWS</i> [m s^{-1}]		S_{hub} [m s^{-1}]		WD_{hub} [$^\circ$]		α (shear)		ψ (veer)	
	<i>MAE</i>	<i>MAE_{re}</i>	<i>MAE_{ob}</i>	<i>MAE_{re}</i>	<i>MAE_{ob}</i>	<i>MAE_{re}</i>	<i>MAE_{ob}</i>	<i>MAE_{re}</i>	<i>MAE_{ob}</i>	<i>MAE_{re}</i>
	<i>obs</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>f</i>
WRF-YSU (ref)	1.26	0.00	1.35	0.00	10.49	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.07	0.00
WRF ensemble	1.16	0.63	1.12	0.76	14.24	5.14	0.11	0.05	0.07	0.02
WRF-YSU_LES	1.51	0.45	1.60	0.54	10.67	4.09	0.15	0.05	0.06	0.03
WRF-VentosM_ke	1.56	0.69	1.59	0.72	10.74	6.34	0.12	0.05	0.06	0.03
CFDWind1D_ke	1.56	0.63	1.62	0.68	11.49	6.22	0.15	0.09	0.06	0.05
Alya-CFDWind1D_ke	1.48	0.73	1.42	0.70	11.30	2.90	0.14	0.07	0.07	0.02
Ellipsys1D_ke	1.37	0.55	1.50	0.61	11.51	5.22	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.04
Ellipsys3D_ke	1.36	0.66	1.52	0.74	10.61	5.17	0.16	0.09	0.06	0.04
Ellipsys3D_LES	1.38	1.13	1.37	1.27	11.90	11.99	0.18	0.09	0.09	0.06
SP-Wind_LES	1.47	0.63	1.38	0.69	8.79	3.25	0.13	0.04	0.07	0.02

Figure 5: Time-height contours of horizontal wind speed S , direction WD , potential temperature Θ and turbulent kinetic energy TKE . Dotted lines denote a rotor diameter of 160 m at 120 m hub-height.

Figure 6: Time series of rotor-based quantities of interest used for validation.

Figure 7: Vertical profiles of wind speed, wind direction and potential temperature at UTC 2006-07-02 00:00:00.

WRF-YSU_LES is the closest to the reference, which is to be expected since they are results from different nests of the same simulation. Still, differences are significant of around 0.5 m s^{-1} of wind speed and 4° of wind direction at hub-height. Microscale models increase the error by $0.2\text{-}0.7 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ of wind speed and up to 7° of wind direction at hub-height with respect to the WRF-YSU_LES results. With respect to observations, all simulations show similar results with a *MAE* of $1.1\text{-}1.6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ of wind speed and up to 14° of wind direction at hub-height. Considering vertical wind speed shear and wind direction veer, SP-Wind and the WRF ensemble produce the closest results to the reference WRF simulation.

Different sets of $k\text{-}\epsilon$ constants have been tested (not shown) leading to changes that are within the spread shown in Figure 6, which is also comparable to that observed in the WRF sensitivity analysis when changing the planetary boundary-layer scheme.

Recently, capabilities of EllipSys3D have been extended to cover wall modeled LES of stratified flows and at the same time, a “striped” down 1D version of the code have been made operational [28]. Figures 5 and 6 and Tables 2 and 3 show a general good agreement between URANS based EllipSys1D and EllipSys3D computations. Some minor differences exist though; a possible cause of them might be related to the fact that the vertical velocity (W) and the advection terms are implicitly assumed to be zero in the EllipSys1D. Further investigations are necessary to confirm this.

Initial LES computations based on coarse grid resolution and very basic Smagorinsky SGS model show that EllipSys3D LES is capable of reproducing the basic LLJ features observed at the Cabauw site, but Tables 2 and 3 *MAE* comparisons and Figures 2 and 3 indicate that significantly higher resolution and a more advanced approach to SGS turbulence modeling are needed in order to capture all main details relevant for its application in a wind energy context.

Regarding VENTOS[®]/M wind speed results, both Figures 5 and 7 show that the LLJ magnitude was reasonably well predicted. The diurnal cycle of the simulation wind speed shows over-predictions around 1.4 m s^{-1} , affecting the *REWS* and S_{hub} error values in Table 2 which are higher than the reference simulation. Good agreement was obtained for the wind direction, shear and veer regarding their integrated error. Analysis of Figure 6 indicates a generalized under-prediction of α for several nocturnal periods, analogous to a higher turbulent shape factor of the boundary-layer. These mismatches happen also with WRF and, despite the VENTOS[®]/M limitations of its heat-flux boundary condition, the microscale simulation predicts higher values of α and closer to the observations. The results further show a -2.5 K temperature bias that occurs in both WRF and VENTOS[®]/M results, as well as in the other microscale simulations, which originates from the ERA-Interim input data.

Table 3: *MAE* with respect to the reference mesoscale simulation for unstable ('u': $z/L < -0.2$), neutral ('n': $-0.2 < z/L < 0.2$) and stable ('s': $z/L > 0.2$) conditions.

	<i>REWS</i> [m s^{-1}]			S_{hub} [m s^{-1}]			WD_{hub} [$^\circ$]			α (shear)			ψ (veer)		
	<i>U</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>s</i>
WRF-YSU (ref)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
WRF ensemble	0.45	0.51	0.82	0.51	0.60	1.02	5.79	8.98	3.97	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.03
WRF-YSU_LES	0.48	0.44	0.42	0.58	0.72	0.48	4.59	4.15	3.62	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.03
WRF-VentosM	0.64	0.75	0.74	0.68	0.80	0.73	9.74	7.02	3.10	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.03
CFDWind1D_ke	0.74	0.45	0.56	0.73	0.53	0.65	5.62	7.87	6.53	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.05	0.09	0.05
Alya-CFDWind1D_ke	0.79	0.39	0.72	0.78	0.51	0.66	4.66	3.16	1.24	0.09	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.03
Ellipsys1D_ke	0.58	0.40	0.55	0.57	0.40	0.69	4.30	7.47	5.75	0.06	0.12	0.13	0.03	0.10	0.05
Ellipsys3D_ke	0.67	0.47	0.68	0.67	0.60	0.83	4.13	8.03	5.70	0.04	0.14	0.13	0.02	0.10	0.04
Ellipsys3D_LES	0.56	1.27	1.64	0.59	1.06	1.93	11.69	8.36	12.81	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.02	0.05	0.11
SP-Wind_LES	0.48	1.36	0.66	0.50	1.38	0.76	3.00	1.72	3.71	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.03

Finally, Table 3 shows the MAE_{ref} is computed for different stability classes filtering with the observed stability parameter z/L , where L is the Obukhov length and $z = 10 \text{ m}$: unstable

('u': $z/L < -0.2$), neutral ('n': $-0.2 < z/L < 0.2$) and stable ('s': $z/L > 0.2$). Not all the models behave similarly depending on stability. The WRF ensemble *REWS* is more sensitive in stable conditions. This is also the case for Ellipsys3D_LES probably due to the coarser resolution of the simulation compared to the other LES simulations that do not show this high sensitivity in stable conditions.

In general, it is difficult to extract more meaningful conclusions from Table 2 and Table 3 due to the limited statistical significance of the samples. The overall assessment would be richer if several diurnal cycles from uncorrelated synoptic conditions would have been tested. The ensemble WRF simulations for the same cycle already show significant improvement on mean flow quantities.

5. Conclusions

Results of the GABLS3 diurnal cycle benchmark with an emphasis on rotor-relevant values are presented. The main challenge for microscale models was to produce consistent flow fields with respect to the mesoscale model that was used to derive their input forcings. This consistency has been achieved by both LES and URANS models. The spread of the models is significant but of similar magnitude as that shown by WRF using different boundary-layer parameterizations. The input uncertainty coming from the mesoscale, even in relatively ideal conditions, is large and results in *MAE* of wind speed at hub-height of the order of 1.1-1.6 m s^{-1} over the whole cycle and hourly errors of up to 3 m s^{-1} . This is partly mitigated when using an ensemble average of several simulations which also lead to better results in terms of wind shear and wind veer.

By ensuring consistency of the microscale models at introducing input forcings we can proceed with further analysis on how RANS and LES models interpret the structure of turbulence in different stability conditions.

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